

PUBLIC TRANSPORT IMPROVEMENT PRINCIPLES BASED ON INTEGRATED MARKETING CONCEPT

Tashkent State Transport University

"Transport economy" department

The senior teacher is

Giyosidinov Boburbek Baxtiyor o`g`li

bgiyosidinov@gmail.com

Abstract: According to the experience of foreign countries, it is necessary to improve the public transport system in order to create an ecological transport system, reduce traffic load, ensure traffic safety and ensure social stability of the society.

Key words: transport, public transport, principle, integrated marketing, concept

The analysis of different marketing concepts shows that a more integrated marketing concept is suitable for managing the marketing activities of public transport. One of the founders of this concept was F. Kotler and K. L. Keller. According to them, "integrated marketing is formed on the basis of two principles: first, marketing activities are carried out to offer displacement and value; and secondly, all marketing activities should be aimed at forming the sum of the results. In other words, the development and implementation of all marketing activities should be reflected in the marketing activities of the enterprise or organization. That is, demand management, resource management and collaborative systems management should be integrated in the organization.

The integrated marketing part of this concept, management of exchange processes, can be applied not only at the regional level, but also at the city level. For this reason, in our opinion, the concept of integrated marketing at the city level is understood as an activity aimed at meeting economic, social and environmental needs and wants.

The main features of the integrated marketing concept are as follows:

- All marketing activities carried out within the framework of integrated marketing should be carried out by striving for one goal, and mutual actions should be coordinated;

- The integrated approach is complex, and all marketing tools should be directed to achieve the set goal;

- The elements of marketing and the content within them are interconnected and interrelated, forming actions in one direction.

Those who die carrier operators to the population service show marketing different character advertising events , sales encouraging shares transfer of the population needs to learn transport service types expansion , service culture upgrade with done increase need will be

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Based on this goal, the main tasks of marketing activities in public transport are as follows:

1. Studying the needs of transport service users;
2. Improving the quality and culture of transport service;
3. Development of public transport infrastructure;
4. Managing the behavior of consumers, taking into account their wishes;
5. Providing public transport services to the population and encouraging their use;
6. Improving the status (image) of public transport;
7. Organization of communications with the public;
8. Implementation of "green economy" requirements, preservation of the external environment, etc.

In order to effectively perform these tasks, there are basic requirements, that is, principles of public transport marketing management. Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan " On Transport" contains the main principles of transport-

related activities. They include: legality; security; environmental cleanliness; being able to use transport services; openness and transparency. We believe that the principles of using public transport provided by us are mostly adequate. However, in order to satisfy the population with transport services, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for compliance with these principles, to demonstrate the possibility of using marketing tools.

in "Bolshaya ekonomicheskaya encyclopedia" refers to the following basic principles of marketing:

1. taking into account the needs, the state and dynamics of demand and the market situation in making business decisions that ensure the best results;

2. creation of conditions for adaptation of production to market requirements, structure of demand not to current benefit, but in the long term. This includes market research and segmentation, determination of unsatisfied customer requirements, affecting the development and sale of goods and taking into account the customer's interest in them;

3. encourage customers to purchase the same product by targeting and sequentially influencing the market, customers and consumers;

4. during the formation of the firm's long-term and appropriate activity, forecasting in market research and the purchase of necessary goods on the basis of it, the ability to fully satisfy the needs of customers;

5. orientation to a clear commercial result, achieving the result, the company has a position in the market suitable for long-term goals.

The implementation of marketing principles is related to the development of appropriate marketing programs.

In our opinion, we can include the following in these principles:

—Being focused on the needs of users of transport services;

—Duration of relationship with users of public transport services;

—Formation of strategic values in cooperation with users of transport services.

Strategic values include stable and efficient operation of public transport, high quality of transport service, compliance with safety and environmental requirements, ability to meet the needs of all groups of passengers (for example, people with limited mobility) and others:

- Complexity (comprehensively);
- Speed (operability);
- The presence of feedback.

The principle of feedback is one of the main ones in the management of marketing activities of public transport. The reason for this is the need to replace the one-way communication used by marketers (advertising, preferential offers, brochures, price lists, printed materials about goods and services, warranty cards) with two-way communication to convey the necessary information to consumers and shape their future behavior. comes out.

In addition, we can include the following principles in the category of basic principles of effective organization of public transport:

impunity; timely (on the basis of the studied schedule) and speedy transportation; compliance, i.e. compliance with established procedures; information security and reliability; and affordability .

1 – picture. The main factors of organizing marketing activities of public transport¹

As the process of information and digitalization increases, the organization of marketing activities of the public transport mentioned above is becoming more complicated. One of the main reasons for this is the growing awareness of the population, increasing demands for services, the need to create comfort as much as possible and other factors. For example, the introduction of the Wi - Fi system on bus route 14 of Tashkent increased the number of passengers. But, for some reason, this practice is becoming widespread. However, using the Internet is a necessity of life.

In Figure 1 , creating feedback with passengers, providing necessary sources of information, especially the Internet, is the basis for changing the attitude of the population to public transport, encouraging its use, and organizing the provision of various services (see Figure 1).

Implementation of tasks of marketing research of the public transport system based on the above-mentioned principles leads to the achievement of the efficiency of the entire system and corresponds to the concept of "Reform of the public transport system" of the republic leadership. There are several factors that can be taken into account in increasing the inclination of the passengers, and the following can be included in their composition :

- variety of transport services;
- service quality and culture;

¹ Compiled by the author

- presence of feedback with passengers;
- availability of reputation (image) of passenger carriers;
- professionalism and responsibility of drivers;
- compliance with safety and environmental requirements;
- optimality of directions;
- convenience of vehicles, cleanliness, etc.

The influence of public transport marketing on the passenger's decision to use public transport is shown in the figure below .

A passenger uses his previous experience and satisfaction in his decision to choose and use public transport. For this reason, representatives of public transport should focus on improving the quality of transport services, creating a system of creating convenience and benefits for passengers. Of course, in the era of digitalization, it is necessary for them to create a system for providing adequate information to the population, implementing advertising and PR campaigns, and providing information about themselves and their services to the Internet. This includes making flyers with information about available traffic, route maps, connecting points for bus, taxi and subway services.

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